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From Office to Home: Reading Melville’s “Bartleby, the Scrivener” and Kafka’s “Metamorphosis” as Texts in Dialogue

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Abstract:

Herman Melville’s “Bartleby, the Scrivener” (1856) and Franz Kafka’s “Metamorphosis” (1915) have always shared a peculiar resonance. Comparative analysis of the two texts by scholars like L. Fallon Duncan and Maurice Friedman often demonstrated how both texts highlight human alienation, isolation, and confinement of non-productive entities in a modern, industrialized, and capitalist society. This paper departs from the conventional comparative framework and argues that the two texts are in dialogue with each other. By placing the texts as companion pieces, we will first discuss how, between Bartleby and Samsa, the oeuvre of non-action and non-verbal protest against regimental utilitarian life extends from office into the home. It will then analyze how the tyranny of the clock and time, which primarily governed public and professional life in Bartleby’s world, emerges as a dominating force in Samsa’s domestic existence. The paper will conclude with a brief discussion on various adaptations of both texts, being continually reimagined in newer formats like video games, graphic novels, and VR experiences.

Keywords: Alienation, Cultural Appropriation, Industrialization, Literary Afterlife.

Introduction

Herman Melville's "Bartleby, the Scrivener" (1856) and Franz Kafka's "Metamorphosis" (1915) have always invited comparison. Scholars like L. Fallon Duncan and Maurice Friedman have often traced thematic parallels in the portrayal of human alienation, isolation, and confinement of non-productive entities in a modern, industrialized, and capitalist society. The present study makes a departure from this conventional comparative framework and focuses on how the two texts continue to be in dialogue with each other, both in documenting the history of modernity and anticipating its future possibilities. Placing them in dialogue with each other allows us to see the shifting terrain of mechanized life - causing gloom and disillusionment - migrating from the workplace into the private sphere. Reading the texts as companion pieces also highlights how Bartleby's and Gregor Samsa's non-active and non-verbal protest against the dominance of time spreads from office to home. Together, the two texts form an archive showing how, during the intervening years, private space shrank under the pressure of mechanized time and utilitarian demands. Placing Bartleby and Samsa as texts in dialogue also allows us to trace a history in continuity. Reading them in sequence gives us a deeper understanding of how the texts continue to be relevant in the present time. Their relevance is evident in their inclusion as canonical texts across university curricula, as well as in their reinvention through contemporary formats such as online columns, video games, graphic novels, and VR experiences. With increasing cases of depression, solitariness, burnout and frustration both in work place and home, the sheer popularity of interactive adaptations of both Bartleby and Samsa amongst youngsters indicates that they are perfectly in sync both with each other and with the present younger generation, meanwhile the rest of the world continues to grapple with the breakdown of their verbal language.

From Office to Home: Expanding oeuvre of non-Action

Written in first person, Melville's "Bartleby, the Scrivener" (A Story of Wall Street) is about a law copyist named Bartleby who is employed by the narrator, a veteran lawyer with an office on Wall Street. Though peculiar in his solitary ways, Bartleby begins to work as an able copyist for the lawyer. In a short while, however, a significant change comes over him when he denies his employer's demand to 'check copy' with the apathetic statement "I prefer not to" (Melville 17). Leo Marx observes that this incident is followed by Bartleby repeatedly denying any demands of his employer that do not involve his core duty, which is to write and copy. This leads to a series of unfortunate events that adversely affect Bartleby. Under his 'prefer not to' refrain, he is unable to enjoy his privileges within the civil society that responds by isolating and confining him. He is forcefully evicted from the lawyer's office and is sent to jail, where he eventually dies. The story ends with an anecdote that informs the reader that Bartleby was a subordinate clerk in the Dead Letter Office. This detail is meant to provide a logical reasoning for Bartleby's peculiar mind. As the story ends with a presumptuous cry by the narrator, "Ah, Bartleby! Ah, humanity" (Melville 64), it suggests how Melville shows that a life reduced to a routine and mechanized regimen of professional life contributed to existential decay. Reading Franz Kafka's "Metamorphosis" in continuity with Melville's story, it feels as though from this point onwards, something deeper begins to unfold. "Metamorphosis" begins with a startling estrangement from the human body and a quiet unraveling of humanity, all within the supposed safety of the home. It is a grotesque story of a young travelling salesman, Gregor Samsa, who awakens from a troubled sleep, only to find himself inexplicably metamorphosed into an insect. Like Bartleby, this seminal change in Samsa's being is followed by several unfavorable incidents that isolate, confine, and eventually kill him in his room. Though the deaths of both Bartleby and

Samsa bring relief to those around them, readers have often found these endings as powerful expressions of defiance and resistance. Being non-conformists in their own way, their death has often been seen as the ultimate non-verbal and non-violent protest against a society that had begun to value productivity over humanity, obedience over individuality. If seen as complementary narratives, the story of a man's passive resistance to social norms of labor, when it crosses the technological and mechanical progress of six decades, becomes an involuntary resistance of the body towards a system that has enslaved the mind to give constant labor.

The years that span between 1856 and 1915 are seminal to understanding the way we experience life today. With rising industrialization, mechanization, and urbanization, these years set the stage for the dynamic world of artificial intelligence we see today. Alongside this history of technological and mechanical progress lies a darker history of labor and migration that also demands attention. Scholars like Ranabir Samaddar have shown that the history of the late 19th and early 20th century can be revised by focusing on labor history and migration patterns. Bartleby's and Samsa's stories seem to both document this paradoxical history while subtly predicting the future. When read as extensions of each other, the gloom and non-action that characterized Bartleby's work life appear to spread and engulf Samsa's domestic life. Taking place on Wall Street, Melville places his peculiar protagonist at the heart of the financial and material progress of America. Leo Marx, in his article "The Machine in the Garden," discusses how the industrial revolution of the nineteenth century was experienced differently by America. Marx argues that, "here, for one thing, the Revolution was delayed, and when it began it was abrupt, thorough, and dramatic" (27). He further stated that American writers like Hawthorne, Melville and Emerson were responding to this "abrupt" and "dramatic" process of mechanization that led to dominance of man-made machines and inventions over nature, in a conceited way. Rather than

talking about the actual imagery of machines or industries, these authors focused on talking about loss anxiety and dislocation. While his essay focuses on works like Hawthorne's "Ethan Brand" and also Melville's *Moby Dick*, it is relevant for Melville's "Bartleby, the Scrivener". Placed amongst characters like Turkey, Nippers and Ginger Nut and also the lawyer, who's entire being was defined by their relevance to the Wall Street office, Bartleby appears to be a haunting anomaly. His negative affirmations appeared as a passive but potent rupture in the rhythm of capitalist routine, which promoted loss, anxiety, and dislocation amongst people. Though the story does not directly talk about the heightened industrialization and mechanization that America witnessed during the mid-Nineteenth Century, it shows its effect through Bartleby's silent withdrawal and gradual erasure from civil society. When read as an extension to Melville's story, Kafka's Gregor Samsa appears to be a renewed and conditioned version of Bartleby, albeit with an ancient connection. In Samsa's case Lawyer's office is replaced by the home. Disapproving, violent, and patronizing colleagues and strangers of Bartleby's world are replaced by family members - especially Samsa's father and his sister Greta - and also house helpers. When we first meet Gregor Samsa, he is in his room, metamorphosed into an insect. As Samsa's mind battles to move and get ready, we find his body in an adamant state of defying all such attempts. While Bartleby could take recourse to mechanical repetition to withstand the repetitive and exploitative nature of office work, Samsa's body abandons human language and responds to his utilitarian family members in animal-like sounds. Trapped in his metamorphosed insect-like body, Samsa's mind is unable to accept the inertia of a busy, corporate, machine-like life. This is evident in the way Samsa continuously thinks about the time and the fact that he is getting late for the office. His body, however, reacts differently. Like Bartleby, Samsa's physical being, his organs, and his muscles refuse to follow the regime that his mind holds on to. In a way, his mind continues to be enslaved

by the profit and productivity-driven world; his body, however, takes Bartleby's path. It *prefers not* to be human.

Spreading dread of the Clock and Time

As non-action spreads from office to home, so does the dread of the clock and time. The rigid regime of the clock that determines the lives of the Wall Street lawyer and his employees in Melville's story now becomes a threatening presence in Gregor Samsa's private room. If the two stories are read as texts in dialogue, one observes that the 'time' which Bartleby somehow manages to disrupt within the lawyer's office, becomes unyielding as we enter Gregor Samsa's world. In this shift, we can see the possibility of tracing the history that the clock and time underwent as society matured from the Industrial Revolution to a highly Industrialized world.

As Melville's story begins, we find ourselves located within the unnamed narrator's world, which is fairly organized and structured. Weeks are divided into work days and Sundays. The narrator informs us that Sundays are when Wall Street is deserted. A typical workday is further divided into work time, break time, and closing time. It is a source of great humor for the reader and a matter of concern for the lawyer that two of his employees have bizarre routines. Turkey, the senior clerk, becomes overwhelmed after midday and begins to make mistakes: "all his blots upon my documents were dropped there after twelve o'clock, meridian." (Melville 7). The lawyer's growing concern over Turkey's "too energetic" (Melville 7) ways after twelve o'clock and suggesting that he should consider working only in the mornings indicates that any deviation from the routine of a workday was uncomfortable and unacceptable. Turkey's vehement opposition to this proposal faintly addresses the fear of losing one's position and thereby the income. His second employee Nippers, a young copyist, struggles with a peculiar restlessness that disallows him to focus on work

before noon - "It was fortunate for me that, owing to its peculiar cause—indigestion— the irritability and consequent nervousness of Nippers, were mainly observable in the morning, while in the afternoon he was comparatively mild" (Melville 13). Despite these peculiarities, the lawyer's office worked like a perfectly oiled machine, a well-running clock where each part has a specified role. Till noon, which can be seen as the first quarter of a workday - Turkey worked through the lawyers' documents; thereafter, Nippers, whose anxiety and nervous episodes subsided by this time, took over. This is evident when the lawyer remarks that, "Their fits relieved each other like guards. When Nippers' was on, Turkey's was off; and *vice versa*. This was a good natural arrangement under the circumstances" (Melville 13). It is probably this clockwork-like arrangement that allowed both Turkey and Nippers to remain employed by the lawyer. In this meticulously chaotic office. Bartleby was hired to bring another dimension of balance between Turkey and Nippers, while fulfilling the increasing need for scribes at the time. Such was the need for more order and balance in the office that the lawyer informs the reader that he hired Bartleby after a few words about his qualifications. He was happy that the new scribe would be beneficial for his office as his 'sedate' nature would somehow balance the flighty temper of Turkey, and the fiery one of Nippers"(Melville 13). It is important to mention that while the lawyer unconsciously runs his office like a well-oiled clockwork, his concept of time reminds one of an older world order. Elizabeth Freeman, in her study of Bartleby's defective chronicity, observes that, "By naming his employees after purely physical characteristics and counting on their habits—naturalized, perhaps even racialized, as complexion—to mark the days, mornings, meridians, afternoons, and evenings, the lawyer arrogates clock time back to natural time, beating the mechanical time of wage capitalism, and exempting himself from the anxiety-making tempo of Wall Street" (Freeman 130). Extending this interpretation, it can be suggested that the lawyer was

Melville's attempt to preserve a world that was quickly being overtaken by a more mechanical concept of time. Returning to *Bartleby*, it is curious to note that, for two days, Bartleby worked relentlessly. We are told that, "He ran a day and night line, copying by sun-light and by candle-light" (Melville 17). The disruption of temporal norms begins from the third day, when Bartleby *preferred not* to do the copying asked by his employer. Following this, one witnesses a complete stagnation of time and routine in the lawyer's office, as has been established before. Everything that Bartleby does or does not do from this point onward defies what the clock had come to mean in an industrial society. Bartleby preferred not to conform to the dictates of mechanized time, posing a potential threat to a world order built on the transaction of time and labor.

Six decades later, when Gregor Samsa's body follows Bartleby's path and silently 'prefers not to' wake and go to his office, we witness the overwhelming force accumulated by mechanized time. Galili Shahar, in his article on time in Kafka's text, notes that "It is both the fear of time and the anxieties of not-being-in-time into which Gregor Samsa awakes one morning out of 'uneasy dreams'" (257). Time in Samsa's world is not just an indicator of the day; it is a threatening reminder of Samsa's inability to be useful anymore. The dominant presence of the alarm clock and the repeated reference to train timings, timetables, etc. show that the regimen of time that characterized Bartleby's workplace has now infiltrated Samsa's domestic space, and there is no escape from the same. Unlike Bartleby, who lives among office mates and strangers and suffers at their hands, Samsa is amongst his family. The intolerance of unproductivity that characterized the busy world of 1850s Wall Street is now a normalized trait of a middle-class European household. The physical and emotional violence that Samsa suffers at the hands of his father, sister and also the cleaning lady casts a dark shadow on how the modern world has progressed. In his comparative analysis of Samsa and Bartleby, L. Fallon Duncan connects the violent outbursts of Gregor

Samsa's father with Turkey's and Nippers's aggressive reactions to Bartleby's negative affirmation. While this similarity is unmissable, the basic difference in their situation is more telling in understanding the texts. While Bartleby is attacked and hurt by people from work, Samsa is hurt by his family. While Bartleby is being punished by people for wasting everybody's work time, and Samsa is violently penalized for being unable to utilize his personal time as well.

In this wasting of regimental and mechanized time, Bartleby and Samsa are forever connected. While Bartleby's non-compliance shows what the utilitarian work culture does to people like him who *prefer not to* be overworked or exploited by peers and seniors, Samsa's non-conformist act shows how conditional and transactional family as an institution could become in a society that is driven by profit and production. Collectively, Bartleby's and Samsa's stories document the spread of a totalitarian regime from office to family, indicating a significant shift that the world underwent as it progressed through industrial and mechanical progress.

Appropriation of Bartleby and Gregor Samsa.

Despite being texts that remained underappreciated and underread in their own time. Bartleby and Gregor Samsa have enjoyed a unique and unusual afterlife. There are two notable film productions, Anthony Friedman's British film made in 1970, and Jonathan Parker's American film with shades of comedy made in 2001. Along with this, there is a metafictional Spanish novel, *Bartleby and Co.*, by Enrique Vila-Matas, and numerous references in theoretical works. It is curious to note that a parallel was drawn between Bartleby's tale and the 'Occupy Wall Street' protests that took place in the US in 2011. Hannah Gersen who in her article made this connection with Bartleby and the protest states that, "the parallels between Bartleby's peculiar form of rebellion and the protestors of Occupy Wall Street should be obvious" (Gersen), this is because

the 'Occupy Wall Street' movement and the other 'Occupy' movements across the country in general are about the struggles of America's dwindling middle class. It is fascinating to see how, in most of these retellings and reimaginations, Bartleby emerges as a powerful figure whose passive yet firm disobedience resonates with the working class and continues to generate meaning and relevance. Similarly, Kafka's "Metamorphosis" has been adapted by artists and scholars many times. Scholars like Stanley Corngold in *Lambent Traces: Franz Kafka* argue that Kafka's existential themes and narrative style in texts like *Metamorphosis* make them endlessly adaptable to postmodern anxieties. Thus, we see Gregor Samsa's story adapted as films and plays. Some notable examples include the 1975 Czechoslovakian film, directed by Jan Nemeč, and the 2012 British live-action film directed by Chris Swanton. In theatre, Steven Berkoff's *Metamorphosis* (1969) can be seen as a significant adaptation. Berkoff's play used physical theatre and expressionist aesthetics to bring alive the story of Gregor Samsa on stage. In all these references and retellings, both texts remain relevant for the way they resist the industrial and capitalist demands on one's life.

A curious change takes place in the afterlife of both the text post 2015. In 2018, *The Economist* launched their new column and titled it "Bartleby." The webpage states that "Our column on work and management muses on the mundanity of working life and the plight of managers, as they attempt to understand what makes their workers tick" (*The Economist*). In 2019, Kafka's *Metamorphosis* got a new facelift when it was adapted as a virtual reality installation. The Goethe Institute in Prague, Czech Republic, adapted Kafka's story into a Virtual reality installation to be experienced by people. On the Goethe Institute's webpage, Mika Johnson - the director, is quoted as saying, "VRwandlung' transfers Franz Kafka's work from the pages of a book to virtual reality. The protagonist is no longer Gregor Samsa, but you." In 2020, a Polish game studio, Ovid Works,

released a video game adaptation of Kafka's story. This game is called *Metamorphosis* and is defined as a 'first-person puzzle platformer' in which the player identifies themselves as Gregor Samsa, transformed into an insect. The game also incorporates elements from Kafka's novel *The Trial*. The irony of these adaptations is remarkable. While Bartleby's quiet yet resolute refusal to participate in a mechanized office life was once a symbol of resistance, it is now repurposed by corporate entities like *The Economist* to inspire productivity by targeting the very employees who might empathize with Bartleby's inertia. Things become almost paradoxical when Kafka's dark tale becomes an object of entertainment via VR reality and video games. Samsa, whose body once rebelled against the degrading routine of the capitalist world, becomes a video game character who is *once again* made to perform a repetitive task of solving puzzles by the players. In VR mode, he is the source character through whom people derive pleasure and thrill while plugged into Samsa's virtual reality world. Tomáš Moravec's article on the Goethe-Institut website. Recounting his experience of the VR show, notes that after being plugged into the machines when the show begins, "A light flashes on and I find myself in 1915, in Gregor Samsa's room in the Old Town of Prague and a completely different body." Discussing his experience further, he writes, "In *VRwandlung*, I am Gregor Samsa. I am a disgusting, confused beetle." Though it is fascinating to see these diverse adaptations, a deep-rooted discomfort persists with such ventures because they seem to turn Kafka's trauma into a consumer item of pleasure and sensational experience. Such cooption and cultural appropriation can lead to substantial dilution and trivialization of various anxieties and insecurities of modern life that authors like Franz Kafka and Herman Melville addressed through their odd protagonists. It also becomes disheartening to witness how attempts are still being made to co-opt figures like Bartleby and Gregor Samsa and make them fit into the social structure.

An alternate reading of these adaptations can be possible only if we shift our focus from fidelity and consider them as dialogues that reflect present-day apprehensions and challenges. Reading them in this light allows us to see such adaptations as attempts to resurrect classic literary works and reframe them to suit the contemporary socio-cultural and political structures, while also exploring the extent to which such texts can impact technological advancement and vice versa. It cannot be denied that by naming an online employee forum as *Bartleby* and casting Gregor Samsa in a video game and VR show, *The Economist*, The Goethe Institute, and the game company Ovid Works pay tribute to important but often overlooked works by authors like Franz Kafka and Herman Melville. It further reveals how two subversive literary icons gradually evolve into experiential stand-ins and immersive experiences for the younger generation who, like the two protagonists, grapple with isolation and social scrutiny. If in these changed circumstances one reads the core texts and their adaptations as texts in dialogue, one can sense how *Bartleby* and Kafka continue to be relevant collectively. While these adaptations may appear to digress from the texts' core purpose - to resist and disobey the utilitarian industrial society - they nonetheless render them relevant to a generation born into a hyper-mechanized world. Their afterlives as interactive formats reflect a shift in how the world today seeks not only to read their stories, but also to embody them. This suggests that a deeper engagement is required with Melville's and Kafka's texts together. Their symbolic potential can still point to the way larger issues of labor, identity, and also agency work in the present times.

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